

THE VERBAL COMMUNICATION BETWEEN MEN AND WOMEN IN DIFFERENT LANGUAGES

Ergasheva Fazilat Botirovna

Surxondaryo viloyati Uzun tumani

1-sonli umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktabining ingliz tili fani o'qituvchisi

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The sociality of the language determines linguistic changes adapted by society and manifested in the language. The interaction between the language and gender of the speaker in a particular language is considered within the research of social variability of the language, which is understood as the socially determined existence of language variants serving various subgroups of the general linguistic community.

The way of men and women speaks has become an interesting topic to study. In some cases, men and women have different ways in using a language. These differences could arise from the structure, form, vocabulary, syntax, and so forth. That men and women have different voice in term of the characteristics such as the difference of using verbal skills. In term of vocabulary, for instance, women normally tend to use colorful words and maintain adjectives such as lovely, sweet, and beloved which are rarely used by men. In short, men and women have different styles of using a language because they are brought up in different ways and they possess different roles in society.

A number of studies related to the differences of language use both men and women were previously conducted by researchers. Men and women had a number of differences in some ways. The term "gender" cannot be avoided in our life as it belongs to a part of societies. Gender and sex itself could have divergent meanings. Some people use those terms synonymously. Indeed, it is needed to define the basic terms and its concepts as it has been separated by the so sociolinguistic researchers. Schilling elaborates that gender is not simply to a biological or physiological sex. It is more than a complicated construct of sociocultural and socio-psychological aspects. With regard to this, gender is often held to be grounded in biological sex. She then emphasizes that gender has to do with matters such as social and economic roles and relations (including, crucially, power relations), conceptualizations of masculinity and femininity, and often also with sexual orientation and sexual identity. It can be inferred that sexuality tends to has to do with biological aspects. On the other hand, gender is a social construct or socioculturally determined.

Language, as the most important communication tool, is one of the indispensable elements of the existence of societies. Language is the greatest power in people's perception and evaluation of the world, in transferring cultures and ideologies. Therefore, language is never an issue that can be ignored in social studies. The language is only a small part of that integral phenomenon that we aspire to cognize, which necessarily involves not only the memory, physiological, psychological, psycho-physiological properties of the person, but also the knowledge of the world, the social context of utterances, the ways of interaction and organization of all types of the knowledge, as well as all human activities. A discourse as the result of socialization –the comprehension of the

surrounding world by an individual, his/her involvement in reality. Primary socialization (family, education) and secondary socialization (information received by an individual from messages of mass media) represent a single mechanism of personality formation in the information society. "It is a discourse which serves as the main tool for the socialization of a person, his/her involvement in the public and political life".

If to make an "individual understand a discourse strategically as an action in an ongoing social interaction sequence means that the hearer makes assumptions about the intentions, purposes, wishes, preferences, beliefs, opinions, attitudes, ideology, emotions, and personality of the speaker" etc. , we assume that a language, in essence, in line with its terminology system has the potential to create a discourse and send it to the audience based on particular strategy on behalf of the official agency, entity, etc. Feminists also drew attention to the importance of language in gender studies and brought the language and feminism fields together and put the language issue in a very central place in feminism studies. Under this lies the constant influence of language and behavior on each other.

The masculine language takes the man as the norm, which makes the woman invisible. It means that the reality of the whole world is based on men. The identity formation and subjectivity of women who cannot find their place in language is negatively affected, and thus the identity of women exists in relation to the identity of men. In the light of these observations and knowledge, some feminists (such as radical feminist Mary Daly) have taken this issue seriously enough to suggest "a radical deconstruction or deconstruction of language". According to them, in order to create a new reality, it is necessary to work on new terms, new words and to neutralize language. Although this will require a long and exhausting process, feminists have taken the most important step by drawing attention to this issue and creating sensitivity. Against this background, world languages reflect sexism in direct proportion to their culture. Sexism in language can take two forms. First, the system of the language itself is sexist (as in languages that divide words into masculine-feminine); second, the way we use language is sexist (as in semantically gendered languages). The fundamental approach to gender and language studies dates back to the early XX century. Gender aspect of language and communication had been the main subject of the researches but still remaining invisible to the linguistics. The development of sociolinguistics, the formation of the post modern theory of knowledge and the rise of the feminist movement played an important role in the emergence of fundamental gender issues, as an independent aspect within an interdisciplinary field. Data gathered indicate an identification of (male) man with human being. However, the feminist theory explains the identification by distribution of gender roles in society, rather than linguistic factors, since according to the sociolinguistic research, the English language has been developed under influence of Jewish-Christian traditions which supported male dominance over female. According to Pamela Fishman, who studied a conversational activity in "Language, Gender and Society" language is the constructor and keeper of hierarchical status between males and females.

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